

THE CHANGING DRESS EXPERIENCE: INCREASING PRODUCT ATTACHMENT THROUGH SURFACE DESIGN AND MATERIAL DETAILS

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ABSTRACT

Manufactured clothing is commonly produced as a finished product to be worn with minor physical changes after the time of sale. This generates a perception that there is little opportunity to actively engage and modify clothing. Imagine fashion as an open-ended product that changes and evolves over time. This case study sets out to illustrate an approach to increase emotional product attachment. This is achieved through continual change in surface design and material detail of clothing. Garment evolution is directed by creative choices of the owner to reflect personality characteristics. Transformative details and simple natural dye processes help articulate the design as a study to encourage sustainable product attachment.

Keywords: product attachment, apparel design, emotional bonding, natural dye, sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Barely worn clothing is often discarded based on style changes. This creates disconnect between the functional and psychological needs of a garment. There is a need to present opportunities to connect more emotionally with garments for sustainable product attachment. Connecting with a material object through sensory, behavioral and symbolic qualities creates a lasting attachment with the individual to the object (Chapman, 2005). Therefore, it is valuable to create designs that encourage interaction between the individual and the garment. The ability to have some active ownership through physical or conceptual creation of garments is suggested to bring enjoyment to people (Fletcher, 2008). Norman (2004) further

discusses “the best designs are the ones we create for ourselves.” This is also supported by the years of generative research from Sanders (2006) who found deeper user engagement may come from the idea that everyday people want to be more than ‘consumers’ and actually become ‘creators’. Further validation for this case study found in past thesis research, “Creativity in Repurposing Textiles”, illustrates that women specifically have an interest in adapting clothing (Meyer, 2010). This form of self-expression can be an explanation for products serving as a symbol of one’s identity (Govers and Mugge, 2004). Clothing, inherently, is a strong visual indication of identity, making it ideal for encouraging product attachment through self expression.

The design process of this case study is used to illustrate a possible approach to strengthen emotional product attachment through enjoyable engagement of self expression with a selected garment. Structure of the study derives from the Framework of Product Experience by Desmet and Hekkert (2007) in order to understand product attachment. The framework is broken into three types of product experience: aesthetic experience, emotional experience, and experience of meaning. This case study focuses on the experience of meaning. Demonstration of the experience of meaning is found in the study by Govers and Mugge (2004) which suggests attachment increases to a product that has a similar personality to the owner. Ambitions of this design set out to give the owner control of tailoring the garment to his/her personality. The case study will show product transformation through change of surface design and material detail to reflect owner’s individuality.

OPPORTUNITY TO CHANGE THE SURFACE DESIGN OF THE GARMENT

Changing a garment's surface provides a direct method to reflect the personality of the owner. The design in this case study uses natural dyes as a way to adjust color and pattern on the surface. Natural dyes are used because of accessibility and ease of process for owners. If the experience is enjoyable there will be an increased opportunity for product attachment. Savaş (2004) discovered two reasons for product attachment: experience/enjoyment and reflection of self. With the natural dye process, owners of the garment are building memories through the experience while changing the surface design.

THE SURFACE DESIGN PROCESSES

Organic cotton is used because natural fibers better absorb natural dyes. To fix the color and increase lightfastness, alum from a local grocery store is used as a mordant. The mordant is dissolved into boiling water. Then the fabric is added and left to cool overnight. Once dry, a variety of natural dyes can be implemented in the initial design. This iteration uses a delicious blend of berry tea. Water is boiled first, and then tea is added to the dye bath with the fabric. This simple process can be repeated many times to create different variations. It provides the owner a foundation to alter the color based on reflection of self.

As the garment is worn, the owner has the ability to experiment with different processes to change the surface design. For this design, turmeric was dip-dyed to create a yellow accent as a method to refresh the garment after it had been worn a couple of times. Multiple techniques were used to create a range of patterns on the fabric. Later the same segment is used to experiment with plum skins. Pieces of plum skins are hammered into the fabric resulting in a textured effect. This is seen in Figure 1 as an evolution of surface design in one segment of the garment. In further exploration, red cabbage leaves are rolled and then steamed with an iron to generate a line pattern on another segment of the fabric.

There are several benefits to using natural dyes for this design. The materials used to change the surface design can all be found at a local grocery store. Convenience for the owner of the garment is essential. Also, processes used to create the designs involve basic everyday skills such as boiling water, steaming with an iron and hammering. Unlike commercial processes, these sustainable practices produce non-toxic dye baths that have safe disposal. Lastly, natural dyes can fade and change over time which will encourage the owner to continue engagement with the garment through surface design. This helps to build an active relationship with the garment over time to further the product attachment.

Figure 1. Example of surface design evolution. This shows the evolution of surface design on the garment. The fabric was initially dyed with berry tea (far left), was later dip dyed with turmeric (middle), and finally plum skins were pounded into the fabric with a hammer to create a textured effect (far right).

OPPORTUNITY TO CHANGE THE MATERIAL DETAILS OF THE GARMENT

Changing the material details of the garment is an opportunity for the owner to show personality through style characteristics. The design of this garment is created with the intention of transforming a basic shell through the addition of simple segments. Each simple segment for this design is based on rectangular shapes. Consideration of the owner necessitates control over changing material details. The owner is empowered with the ability to reflect their personality characteristics within the garment.

POSSIBILITIES FOR MATERIAL DETAILS

The initial design of this garment is a basic shell that yields a variation of opportunity to add and alter material details. This is created by constructing a simple A-line bodice dress from organic cotton fabric. The inherent possibility of addition and alteration within the bodice is limitless. For this reason, the case study focuses primarily on using rectangular shapes as options for material details. Numerous combinations of rectangular shapes can be explored.

The design in this case study started as a strapless A-line bodice with matching wrap belt. After the garment

is worn a couple of times, the owner can change the details based on personal preferences. For example, a different rectangular piece might be draped around the neckline for a more conservative look. This provides the ability to reflect different personality characteristics for various situational dressing. At any point straps might be added, the bodice lengthened, peplums created, or necklines altered as just a few examples. All of the material details can be manipulated by wrapping, tying, or with simple hook and eye closures. This makes the process of changing the details easy and enjoyable.

CONCLUSION

The case study proposed a design that encouraged product attachment by providing opportunities to emotionally engage in a garment's surface design and material details. Past thesis research from "Creativity in Repurposing Textiles" shows women are interested in creative opportunities to emotionally interact with clothing (Meyer, 2010). Using the Framework of Product Experience by Desmet and Hekkert (2007), this study establishes two ways to enhance product attachment with the experience of meaning. Giving the owner the control to change surface design and material details is a way to impart personality in the

Figure 2. Example of changing the material details. This shows the possibilities to change the material details based on using simple rectangular shapes. It provides a way to change the overall style of the garment.

product, thus furthering meaning through experience. On a secondary level, aesthetic experience is explored with sensory applications inherent in the aroma of dyes and tactile nature of clothing. As stated in the design implications of Schifferstein and Zwartkruis-Pelgrim (2008), to improve product attachment designers should evoke enjoyment through sensory and aesthetic pleasure. The case study achieves this through sense of smell with natural dyes, and tactile qualities of changing garment details. Also, increased product enjoyment can foster accumulation of memories (Schifferstein and Zwartkruis-Pelgrim, 2008). Each interaction with the design builds a unique memory through active engagement.

FURTHER INVESTIGATION

The two techniques in this case study were used as examples to show how changing the surface design and material details of a garment might increase product attachment. Figure 3 represents a series of possible options with the design. The ability to change the surface design and material details could go beyond natural dyes and simple rectangular shapes. In the future, other technologies would be beneficial to

explore. Changing surface design with use of a laser cutter or smart color changing textiles could provide another option for aesthetic experience. Additional changes in material details could also be explored using Lectra patternmaking software. Future work may include new technologies to engage with a garment and further user feedback of the design.

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Figure 3. Example of the final design. This shows a combination of surface design and material detail changes in the original final design.